

PARTICULAR CHARACTERISTICS OF SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION

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Annotation:

The article is dedicated to the particular theoretical perspective of simultaneous interpretation. Many scholars view interpreting as a form of translation. Based upon that assumption, interpreting studies are supposed to benefit from the theory and research in the field of translation. However, interpreting studies has benefited from translation studies only to a very limited degree. Therefore, particular characteristics of simultaneous interpretation require to be investigated in details prior to analyzing them in practical sense. Interpreting is commonly believed to be one of the most cognitively demanding language tasks. Simultaneous interpreting, also involves processes and skills such as: self-monitoring, memory skills, verbal fluency and concurrent listening and production. In order to provide a high-quality interpretation, the interpreter needs to master all of these above-mentioned skills. The question of interpreters' aptitude has been widely discussed in the context of this article:

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One of the most particular characteristics of simultaneous interpretation is effectiveness, which is really tough to acquire by interpreters. The process is regarded very challenging because the time between original speech and translated speech comprises only three or four seconds. It means that a speaker utters his/her words without stopping and meanwhile, an interpreter must translate the words simultaneously. During this hard procedure, the memory, the rich vocabulary and wide outlook of an interpreter occupy a very crucial importance to successfully accomplish this task. In spite of these above mentioned difficulties, more than 90% of international conferences are held with the greater presence of simultaneous interpreters. Main requirements which are demanded to interpreters go as follows: firstly, while the original speech is being uttered, simultaneous interpreter has to differentiate every single detail by listening very attentively. As Atkinson, Richard C. and Richard M. Shiffrin [1] stated According to the resolution of IACI (International Association of Consultant Interpreters), if a simultaneous interpreter can translate the speech of a

speaker at 80% (as it is not possible to realize a 90-100% interpretation process), it is regarded a successful interpretation process. According to Bartłomiejczyk, [2] sometimes, the speech of some conference participants is very fast; therefore it is very difficult for interpreters to keep up with the pace of the speakers' speech and this complicates the work of interpreters.

Gile, Daniel [3] exemplified that speakers usually perplex interpreters even more by using dialect words and idioms during their speeches. In such cases, interpreters should accelerate all of their treasure of knowledge and falling behind their experience, they ought to show their power. It is a pity that there are very few people who speak slowly in order to facilitate the work of interpreters.

According to Anderson, R. B. [4] It is not an easy work to deal with simultaneous interpretation. In addition, people who work in this profession must possess certain high qualities and features. In the interpretation competency, simultaneous interpreters must follow the qualities which are counted as the most essential ones.

1) Linguistic ability. It comprises of pragmatic competence, in its turn, pragmatic competence is divided into two types.

a) Pragmatic-linguistic competence – according to scholars' opinions, interpreter must know the particular features of certain words and phrases.

b) Socio-pragmatic competence. It means to recognize the functional methods and etiquette and other things that occur in simultaneous interpretation.

2) General understanding. It is the quality with the help of which interpreters are able to build up their special vocabulary relying on their general knowledge about certain topics. In this case, interpreters will be able to accomplish their task without any difficulty.

3) The skill of smooth delivery. The quality with the help of which, interpreters are able to deliver the interpretation relying on their secret strategies.

Howard, Ian [5] considered the activity of simultaneous interpretation to be the peak of oral translation process. That's why there are very high requirements on the preparation of interpreters. Any kind of simultaneous interpreters who wants to succeed must possess the following abilities:

1) The ability of speaking fluently both in source and target language.

2) The speech which is built up in high grammatically and phonetically developed manner.

3) Rich vocabulary in both source and target language.

4) The ability of quick recognizing and finding all kinds of difficult phrase-logical words and clichés.

5) The ability of interpreting correctly and effectively both in source and target language.

- 6) The ability of swift reaction.
- 7) Firm operative memory.
- 8) Highly-focused concentration.
- 9) Mental and physical stamina.
- 10) The ability of working in groups.

Dam, Helle V. [6] clarified in his notes that there is not any organization or union that controls the misunderstandings or mistakes which are made at conferences, therefore, the motto of simultaneous interpretation is “only success and no mistake”. After the conferences finish, the delegates, participants and the chief of conference usually express their gratitude to interpreters. If the work done by interpreters is purely-perfect, a lot of credits and applauses are directed to them and everybody tries to work with them again next time. If the interpretation is a very poor, there will be several reactions created by the participants such as, chatting with each other, tapping their feet or coughing and many other undesirable situations. It is not appropriate to neglect even a tiny detail during interpretation process. As the microphone in the booth is very sensitive, interpreters must be very careful when they are moving.

According to Diriker, E, [7] there are several international organizations for accrediting the skills of simultaneous interpreters. One of the famous one is International Association of Consultant Interpreters – IACI, which was founded in 1953, the knowledge of the members of this association is ranked very high and acknowledged by many other international organizations. There is no need for any examination to get enrolled into this association. In order to be one of the members of this organization, one must need a two-year experience as an interpreter and a master’s degree diploma. As every profession has plus and minus, simultaneous interpretation possesses several merits and demerits, which proves the difficult and easy sides of this profession. Most people argue why simultaneous interpretation is more widely-used than consecutive interpretation. According to the notes by Yagi, S.M, [9] we look into why simultaneous interpretation has more advantages than consecutive interpretation. It has the following advantages:

- 1) The speech of a certain speaker is conducted without any pauses. This enables speakers to keep the attention of listeners constantly and it enables to sense the reaction and feelings of listeners.
- 2) The period of time spent on conferences will not be too long thanks to simultaneous interpretation.
- 3) As foreign languages are developing rapidly, participants of conferences would like to listen to the speeches of speakers in a foreign language. On the contrary, if the speech is conducted in a consecutive interpretation, it will become very boring and time-consuming.

In its turn, simultaneous interpretation has the following disadvantages:

- 1) The cost of hiring simultaneous interpreters and renting the necessary equipment is much higher than consecutive interpretation.
- 2) Two or more than three simultaneous interpreters who know the thematic topic very well are required to invite.
- 3) During simultaneous interpretation, the process of losing main idea and delivering small amount of information happens. Based on the views provided by Kahneman, Daniel [10], the preparation and anticipating the speaker during simultaneous interpretation provides a very successfully accomplished work. Therefore, many speakers make preparation for their speeches in advance of delivery and will gladly give or send a copy to an interpreter who takes the trouble to ask for it. Copies of formal speeches and policy statements by public officials can often be readily gained from their offices or looked up on their Internet web sites. Sometimes a translation of the speech to be delivered will also be made available by the speaker or his institution (known among interpreters as “a Van Doren”) and can be read out by the interpreter if the translation is of good quality. Yet, despite those elementary precautions, every speech still has its surprises. A speaker may change his or her mind at the last minute, discard or amend prepared remarks, and say something quite unexpected. (Be especially alert to this when the speech is marked “Check against Delivery”.) And even an experienced interpreter can be caught off guard by a novel idea, an unusual turn of phrase, a breakthrough in the debate, an eccentric speaker, a spur-of-the-moment argument, an impenetrable accent, a mispronounced key word, a halting delivery, poor sound quality, an obscure reference or acronym, or a deliberately ornate way of saying a perfectly simple thing. Overcoming problems of that kind involves a certain amount of intuition.

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